

Equilibrium Film Pressure of Mixed Monolayers of n -Alcohols and n -Alkoxy Ethanols on Water Surface

G. V. PATIL and H. V. KEER*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Powai, Bombay-400 076

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Equilibrium film pressures of equimolar mixtures of n -long chain alcohols, C_n-OH , and corresponding alkoxy ethanols, $C_n-OC_2H_4OH$, were measured in the temperature range 15-25°. Evaluation of thermodynamic properties such as enthalpy, entropy and Gibbs free energy changes indicated higher potential of the mixed compositions compared to the pure components. Results have been discussed in the light of prevalent theories of thermodynamics of multicomponent monolayers.

It is well-known that monomolecular films of n -long chain alcohols and especially of alkoxy ethanols¹⁻⁸ are efficient water evaporation retardants. Since the resistance to evaporation increases with the film pressure, the knowledge of film pressure is of considerable importance. Further, since the spreading process is determined by the nature of chain-chain and/or chain-water interactions both in the bulk and in the monolayer phase, determination of thermodynamic parameters concerned with spreading for structurally related compounds should be helpful in determining the effect of chain structure on a number of interfacial and bulk properties.

Biswas and coworkers⁴ reported on the equilibrium film pressure on water surface of pure n -long chain alcohols, C_n-OH , and the corresponding alkoxy ethanols, $C_n-OC_2H_4OH$ ($n=14, 16, 18, 20, 22$) in the temperature range 15-35°. However, little literature is available on mixed monolayers. Lomonosova and Trapeznikov⁵ studied mixed monolayers of odd alcohols ($C_{15}-OH$ and $C_{17}-OH$), while Patil *et al*⁶ investigated the pressure-area isotherms, on water surface, of mixed monolayers of hexadecanol ($C_{16}-OH$) and octadecanol ($C_{18}-OH$) with docosanol ($C_{22}-OH$) as a function of mole fraction and temperature. A study was, therefore undertaken to determine the equilibrium film pressure of equimolar mixtures of n -alcohols and n -alkoxy ethanols ($n=16, 18, 22$) over pure water-air interface in the temperature range 15-25°. The medium of pure water was selected since the objective was to develop mixed monolayers which would minimize evaporation loss of water stored in lakes and reservoirs containing potable water only.

Only the even values of n were selected, in order to avoid non-ideal behaviour arising out of the mixing of odd-numbered and even-numbered alcohols. The relevant thermodynamic functions were evaluated and discussed in the light of potential utility of the mixed compositions and prevalent thermodynamic theories of multi-component monolayers.

Experimental

Materials: The preparation of the components, n -alcohols and n -alkoxy ethanols, has been reported elsewhere⁷. The sample mixtures were prepared by weighing the pure components (purity > 99.5%) in the required molar ratio and fusing together at about 10° above the melting point to ensure homogeneous mixing and then cooling to room temperature. The solidified mixtures were then aged for 2-3 weeks and finally ground to a fine powder.

Procedure: The method followed was to place a number of solid specks of the powdered sample on a clean water surface and to measure the maximum final pressure, which remained constant irrespective of the quantity of the sample added on the water surface.

Apparatus: The apparatus for measuring the film pressure was a Wilhelmy vertical-pull film pressure balance. This consisted of a thin rectangular glass slide (microscopic cover slip 2.2 cm × 3.3 cm × 0.02 cm) half-immersed in the water and hanging from one arm fixed to the mirror attachment of a torsion wire assembly described elsewhere⁸. The details of calibration of the balance have been reported earlier⁷. The essential condition of this balance is that the contact angle of the glass cover slip with water should be zero⁹. This was achieved by cleaning the slide thoroughly, half-immersing it in water and then pulling it out slightly upwards for the initial adjustment so that the contact angle was always receding.

The vessel in which the film was formed was cylindrical (8 cm diam and 8 cm height) to which was attached another big vessel of 20 cm diam and of the same height. A film of octadecoxy ethanol (a good water evaporation retardant) was formed over the water surface in the bigger vessel, which was also covered with a thick glass plate. This minimized the decrease in the water level of the experimental vessel due to evaporation during the experimental measurements, the period of which

varied normally between 1 to 2 hr and in some cases 3 to 4 hr. The entire assembly was placed in a thermostat so that the temperature of the water surface could be maintained constant to a desired value within $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

The variation of equilibrium film pressure (π^{eq}) with temperature/composition and relevant thermodynamic data are presented in Tables 1-3 and Figs. 1-3.

Pure alcohols and alkoxy ethanols: Table 1 lists the values of π^{eq} along with those reported by Deo *et al.*⁴. These latter values were obtained at

slightly different temperatures, which are noted in parentheses. In general, the agreement is good. The variation of π^{eq} with temperature is non-linear, except for C₁₂-alkoxy ethanol. π^{eq} at a given temperature decreases with increase in chain-length as was also observed by Deo *et al.*⁴.

Table 2 shows that for positive $d\pi^{eq}/dT$, the process is endothermic and there is an increase of entropy on spreading. On the other hand, negative $d\pi^{eq}/dT$ indicates exothermic process accompanied by decrease in entropy. Further, the molar latent heat of spreading, L_s , and concomitant changes in entropy, enthalpy and Gibbs free energy of spreading (ΔS_s , ΔH_s , ΔG_s) were calculated from the observed temperature variation of π^{eq} employing the following equations¹⁰:

$$L_s = \left(\frac{d\pi^{eq}}{dT}\right) NTA \quad \dots (1)$$

$$\Delta S_s = \left(\frac{d\pi^{eq}}{dT}\right) NA \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\Delta H_s = \left[T \left(\frac{d\pi^{eq}}{dT}\right) - \pi^{eq}\right] NA \quad \dots (3)$$

$$\Delta G_s = \Delta H_s - T\Delta S_s \quad \dots (4)$$

Here, A is the area per molecule in the film at pressure π^{eq} , N the Avogadro's number and T the absolute temperature. The variation of π^{eq} with A has been determined by Patil *et al.*⁶ for the alcohol-alcohol mixtures and by Patil¹¹ for the remaining mixtures at several temperatures. The values of A were directly read from the π^{eq} -A isotherms corresponding to the observed π^{eq} at the specified temperatures.

TABLE 1—EQUILIBRIUM FILM PRESSURE ($\pi^{eq} \times 10^3$ N/m) OF PURE ALCOHOLS AND ALKOXY ETHANOLS

Compounds	Temp. °C		
	15.1	19.9	25
<i>Deo et al.</i> ⁴			
C ₁₂ -OH	35.9 (16.9)	37.8	38.9
C ₁₀ -OH	—	32.7	35.5 (25.5)
C ₈ -OH	—	20.3	28.2 (27.3)
C ₁₂ -OC ₂ H ₄ OH	50.9 (15.5)	52.3 (17.7)	50.6 (25.8)
C ₁₀ -OC ₂ H ₄ OH	47.7 (16.9)	48.1	48.8 (25.3)
C ₈ -OC ₂ H ₄ OH	—	40.0 (19)	47.5
<i>Present work</i>			
C ₁₂ -OH	34.0	37.8	39.7
C ₁₀ -OH	29.0	32.8	34.4
C ₈ -OH	—	21.3	27.5
C ₁₂ -OC ₂ H ₄ OH	50.5	51.9	50.1
C ₁₀ -OC ₂ H ₄ OH	47.1	47.8	48.0
C ₈ -OC ₂ H ₄ OH	—	41.1	46.8

(The values in the brackets represent temperature)

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC PROPERTIES OF PURE ALCOHOLS AND ALKOXY ETHANOLS

Compounds	Temp. °C	$\pi^{eq} \times 10^3$ N/m	$A \times 10^{20}$ m ² /molecule	$d\pi^{eq}/dT \times 10^3$	L_s kJ mole ⁻¹	ΔS_s J mole ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹	ΔH_s kJ mole ⁻¹	ΔG_s kJ mole ⁻¹
C ₁₂ -OH	20	37.9	19.40	0.50	17.06	58.13	21.50	-4.39
C ₁₀ -OH	20	32.8	19.26	0.85	28.85	98.28	32.62	-3.81
C ₈ -OH	20	21.3	18.96	0.85	28.44	96.51	30.82	-2.42
C ₁₂ -OC ₂ H ₄ OH	20	51.9	18.90	-0.04	-3.01	-9.37	-6.35	-3.35
C ₁₀ -OC ₂ H ₄ OH	20	47.8	18.78	0.22	7.27	24.84	9.53	-2.26
C ₈ -OC ₂ H ₄ OH	20	41.1	18.30	3.00	96.74	330.00	101.10	-4.38

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PROPERTIES OF MIXED ALCOHOLS-ALKOXY ETHANOLS

Mixture (1 : 1 M)	Temp. °C	$\pi^{eq} \times 10^3$ N/m	$A \times 10^{20}$ m ² /molecule	$d\pi^{eq}/dT \times 10^3$	L_s kJ mole ⁻¹	ΔS_s J mole ⁻¹ deg ⁻¹	ΔH_s kJ mole ⁻¹	ΔG_s kJ mole ⁻¹
C ₁₂ -OH + C ₈ -OH	20	44.6	18.66	0.55	18.07	61.72	13.09	-5.02
C ₁₂ -OH + C ₁₀ -OH	20	45.3	18.26	0.48	15.43	52.73	10.46	-4.98
C ₁₂ -OH + C ₈ -OC ₂ H ₄ OH	21	51.6	18.50	-0.83	-27.25	-50.9	-33.00	-5.73
C ₁₂ -OH + C ₁₀ -OC ₂ H ₄ OH	20	47.3	18.93	1.23	41.07	140.20	35.67	-5.14
C ₁₂ -OH + C ₈ -OC ₂ H ₄ OH	20.1	46.9	18.60	0.58	18.94	64.66	13.68	-5.27
C ₁₂ -OH + C ₁₀ -OH	20	46.2	18.80	1.93	63.49	218.10	58.22	-5.23
C ₁₂ -OH + C ₈ -OC ₂ H ₄ OH	21	51.6	18.47	-0.27	-8.82	-29.98	-14.55	-5.73
C ₁₂ -OH + C ₁₀ -OC ₂ H ₄ OH	20.1	48.4	18.18	0.48	15.39	52.48	10.08	-5.27

Mixed alcohols and alkoxy ethanols: For the mixed compositions, it may be possible to discuss the results either on the basis of equations (1)-(4), which are applicable to monophasic monolayer, binary homogeneous phase, or using the arguments of Motomura *et al*^{12,13} pertaining to thermodynamics of multi-component monolayers.

The π^{eq} values for alcohol-alcohol mixtures generally show a linear variation with temperature (Fig. 1). At a given temperature, these mixtures show higher π^{eq} values ($\sim 7-8 \times 10^{-3}$ N/m) than those of the pure components. Similar high values are observed for $C_{18}-OC_2H_4OH + C_{22}-OC_2H_4OH$ mixture above 20° (Fig. 2). However, below this

Fig. 1. Temperature variation of equilibrium film pressure (π^{eq}) of pure and mixed alcohols.

temperature, there is a rapid fall in π^{eq} values. For alcohol-alkoxy ethanol mixtures, π^{eq} values generally increase slightly ($\sim 4 \times 10^{-3}$ N/m). The higher π^{eq} values are suggestive of stronger interaction in the surface phase, presumably a consequence of the greater escaping tendency on the part of constituents in the mixed bulk phase, compared to the pure constituent bulk phases. Additional support for this argument stems from the endothermic nature of the homogenization process of constituents in the mixture, which was achieved by heating to the melting point of about 110° , and from the widely different molecular chain length and/or different functional groups at the chain-ends, which results in more loose molecular packing as compared to pure, bulk phases.

A comparison of the ΔS_s values indicates that the spreading from bulk solid to monolayer results

Fig. 2. Temperature variation of equilibrium film pressure (π^{eq}) of pure and mixed alkoxy ethanols.

in a significant positive entropy change. This magnitude of entropy change may be related to crystalline structure of the bulk solid. Negative ΔS_s would suggest that the overall structure of the monolayer is more ordered in the mixture than in the bulk.

Finally, the ΔG_s values for the mixed monolayers are lower (-5.0 to -5.8 kJ/mol) than those for the components (-2.5 to -4.2 kJ/mol); this is indicative of the relative stability and thus higher potential as water evaporation retardant of the mixed monolayer compositions.

The thermodynamic model of Motomura *et al*^{12,13} refers to the equilibrium spreading pressure of two component mixtures on a water surface. When a homogeneous binary bulk phase spreads to form a monolayer consisting of two components, there can be 3 degrees of freedom which could be chosen as temperature, T, pressure, p, and the mole fraction of component 2 in the bulk phase, x_2^b . Holding T and p constant, it can be shown that π^{eq} vs x_2^b curve should have a positive or negative slope depending on whether the mole fraction in the monolayer (x_2^m) is larger or smaller than x_2^b . On the other hand, the variation of π^{eq} with T at constant p and x_2^b can be closely related to the entropy change associated with the spreading process. Next, one may consider the equilibrium of two component bulk phases with monolayer phases of one of the two components. Supposing the monolayer phase of component 1 or 2 to be the coexistent one, it can be shown that π^{eq} should always decrease or increase with x_2^b . Further, the slope of the π^{eq} vs T curve depends only upon the magnitude of apparent partial molar entropy change of the component responsible for the spreading process.

Fig. 1 indicates that for alcohol-alcohol mixture π^{eq} increases continuously over that of the pure components and over the entire temperature range studied. This observation is consistent with the binary bulk phase in equilibrium with a monolayer, which could contain either a single component or two components; no distinction is possible on the basis of the existing data. Further, since $d\pi^{eq}/dT$ is positive, the entropy increases during the spreading process. On the other hand Fig. 2 clearly shows that the π^{eq} vs T behaviour of $C_{16}-OC_2H_4OH + C_{22}-OC_2H_4OH$ and $C_{18}-OC_2H_4OH + C_{22}-OC_2H_4OH$ compositions are similar to those of

$C_{16}-OC_2H_4OH$ and $C_{22}-OC_2H_4OH$, respectively. This unequivocally shows that the binary bulk phase is in equilibrium with a monolayer containing a single component, viz., $C_{16}-OC_2H_4OH$ or $C_{22}-OC_2H_4OH$. The variation of π^{eq} with temperature can be related with the magnitude of the partial molar entropy change of C_{16} - and C_{22} -alkoxy ethanols in the mixed compositions. The behaviour of the mixed alcohol-alkoxy ethanol compositions (Fig. 3) appears too complex to be explained.

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Fig. 3. Temperature variation of equilibrium film pressure (π^{eq}) of alcohol-alkoxy ethanol mixtures.